
Analyzing Social Media Adoption for Promoting CSR: A Study of UAE Healthcare Sector

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ABSTRACT: Despite the significant potential presented by social media and its strategic relevance in driving business activities, its adoption continues to pose a considerable challenge, with rates remaining notably low. The primary objective of this study is to examine the factors that influence the application of social media for the promotion of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in the healthcare industry. To achieve this goal, the research employs the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) to establish a hierarchy and assign importance to the elements that shape the utilization of social media in advancing CSR objectives. The results reveal key drivers that impact the integration of social media for CSR promotion in the healthcare industry. These drivers encompass effective CSR communication, differences among social media platforms, the advantages stemming from social media use, stakeholder expectations, and the chosen implementation strategy. Furthermore, these findings hold the potential to provide important guidance for policymakers and pertinent organizations, aiding them in devising targeted strategies grounded in the specific factors of social media adoption that have demonstrated efficacy in CSR promotion.

KEYWORDS: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Social media adoption, Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), United Arab Emirates (UAE)

I. INTRODUCTION

The progression of communication has been a constant throughout human history. The advent of new technologies has not only accelerated the speed of message dissemination but also expanded its overall reach. Consequently, staying abreast of the latest communication technologies becomes paramount for enhancing marketing effectiveness. To maximize effectiveness in shaping public opinion, businesses must establish a strong bond and connection with the general populace. Garnering the empathy of the masses stands as the optimal approach for advancing one's agenda. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), as highlighted by Ni and van Wart (2015), has proven to be notably efficacious in achieving this aim. Nevertheless, the impact of CSR wanes as one distances from the community directly affected by the actions.

Yet, it remains crucial to mold the viewpoints of those not in immediate proximity. This imperative can be met by skillfully utilizing the Internet, with a particular emphasis on social media. The Internet, notably, offers one of the most cost-efficient means of establishing connections with global markets. Its potential reach is vast; as exemplified by an estimated 1.7 billion internet users in 2009 (Capriotti, 2011), a number that has since burgeoned manifold due to the proliferation of communication infrastructure and increasingly affordable technologies. This dynamic presents a prime opportunity for stakeholders to engage with the wider public (Grayson & Hodges, 2017).

Within the Emirates, the government has integrated the provision of outstanding healthcare and the restoration of public healthcare trust into the UAE Vision 2021 initiative (Unit, 2010). The count of hospitals has witnessed a growth of more than two-fold, with the latest tally standing at 70 (Al-Neyadi *et al.*, 2016). It's worth noting that public healthcare services in the Emirates are exclusively designated for citizens, with expatriates being barred from utilizing these facilities managed by the Ministry of Health (Hamidi *et al.*, 2016). Given that expatriates make up a significant 85% of the overall population, their increasing numbers have concurrently spurred the expansion of the private sector. Consequently, expatriates have become heavily reliant on private medical practices to receive healthcare services.

A total of 60 insurance companies are registered in the UAE, playing a central role in overseeing the financial aspects of the private healthcare sectors. Approximately 51% of the population is covered by either public or private health insurance. This obligation for expatriates to obtain health insurance stems from the prohibition of their access to government facilities (Paulo *et al.*, 2017). The levels of satisfaction experienced can also be influenced by the supportive conduct of the healthcare system. In this regard, Corporate

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Social Responsibility (CSR) emerges as one of the most potent tools for achieving enhanced satisfaction and engagement. In the healthcare sector of the UAE, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) primarily centers around aspects of supply chain management (Khan *et al.*, 2018). To ensure long-term viability, a healthcare system needs to be managed within an organizational framework that is bolstered by adequate resources to effectively address the requirements of public health.

Corporate entities and family-run institutions (Table 1) have upheld a longstanding custom of making meaningful contributions to enhance societal well-being. An illustrative example of this is exemplified by Sheikh Khalifa Bin Zaid Al Nahyan, who established hospitals in Al-Ain and Abu Dhabi, and subsequently expanded this philanthropic endeavor beyond national borders to countries like Pakistan, Bangladesh, and numerous others worldwide (Davidson, 2006). In a similar vein, the Al Fahim Group, a prominent conglomerate within the UAE, has played a pivotal role in bolstering societal welfare. Noteworthy among their contributions is the financial support provided to a Special Care Center catering to children with mental challenges, a venture that goes beyond their healthcare initiatives. Furthermore, the group has taken a holistic approach by inviting children with mental and physical disabilities onto their premises, actively involving them in diverse activities designed to cultivate hope, positivity, and a determination for future success among these students.

Table 1. Healthcare CSR Initiatives in the UAE

Company	Project
Khalifa Bin Zayed Al Nahyan Foundation	Sheikh Khalifa Bin Zaid Al Nahyan Hospitals
Al Fahim Group	Abu Dhabi special care centre (AlFahim, 2018)
VPS Healthcare	1000 free heart surgeries Initiative (VPS healthcare, 2018)
Saadiyat	Donation of an ambulance(Gargash Enterprises) Donations to blood banks
Gargash Enterprise	Medical research on osteoporosis and vitamin D deficiency (Gargash Enterprises)

Likewise, VPS Healthcare, a prominent healthcare consortium in the Middle East, has undertaken numerous healthcare-focused Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) endeavors. These include offering 1000 cost-free heart surgeries for individuals who would otherwise struggle to bear the substantial expenses of such a procedure. In a similar vein, the Gargash Group has extended financial support to blood banks and mobile medical services, while also organizing blood donation drives within their corporate campuses. Furthermore, the Saadiyat Group has taken a comparable approach by supporting a research initiative investigating Vitamin D deficiency and Osteoporosis within the UAE. In regard to the public hospitals within the UAE, their utilization of social media for promoting Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) appears to be relatively limited. Enhancing this aspect should be a focal point for them in order to cultivate improved public relations. Notably, only a handful of private clinics, like the Cleveland Clinic Abu Dhabi, have referenced CSR initiatives on their platforms. For instance, the clinic highlighted its involvement with 'Operation Smile,' offering complimentary surgeries for individuals with cleft lips and palates (Cleveland Clinic Abu Dhabi, 2018).

Various factors contribute to the restricted embrace of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) practices within the healthcare framework of the UAE. These include the emergence of novel diseases and medications, public awareness, media attention, increasing customer dissatisfaction, and the continuous escalation of healthcare costs (Benomran, 2010). The prevailing CSR trends within the healthcare industry of Abu Dhabi underscore the varying degrees of proactivity among different establishments in community service (Alawlaqi and Hammadeh, 2016). Generally, healthcare facilities display hesitancy in embracing CSR initiatives, with primary challenges stemming from deficits in accountability, transparency, and communication with local communities. Nonetheless, there exists a widespread recognition of the significance of CSR, and a shared understanding of its pivotal role in advancing development and well-being.

Furthermore, the Health Authority of Abu Dhabi (HAAD) has recently initiated a fresh social media campaign aimed at inspiring young residents to pursue medical specialties. This campaign involves collaborations with various entities and stakeholders, with the goal of enhancing the representation of female professionals relative to their male counterparts within the medical sector (KPMG, 2017). Striving to enhance their benchmarks and position themselves as leaders in the private healthcare domain of the UAE, Zulekha Hospitals have embraced social media as a crucial channel for communicating their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) efforts to both current and potential patients (Zulekha Hospitals, 2013). However, this study approaches the analysis of these factors in a manner distinct from prior research, aiming to achieve specific goals.

The research aims include:

- To identify the factors influencing the adoption of social media that foster the integration of corporate social responsibility within the healthcare ecosystem.
- To examine the identified elements and their implications for advancing CSR among healthcare practitioners.
- To establish a hierarchy of the key catalysts driving the adoption of social media in the promotion of CSR within the healthcare sphere.

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II. LITRATURE REVIEW

CSR has been a longstanding presence within the business landscape. Across the globe, organizations have undertaken various forms of engagement in CSR endeavors (Siniora, 2017). Although a definitive description of CSR remains elusive, scholars generally concur that it entails business enterprises actively contributing to society in a positive manner (Tai and Chuang, 2014). The fundamental tenet of CSR is rooted in the notion that businesses should not exclusively pursue profit maximization; rather, they should extend their focus beyond financial gains to encompass activities that yield favorable impacts on society at large. The underlying rationale for such public contribution lies in the substantial resources at the disposal of business entities, encompassing both human capital and the natural environment. As stewards of these resources that drive their operations, corporations are encouraged by numerous scholars to safeguard and nurture them (Aupperle *et al.*, 1991), an approach deemed essential for the interests of corporations.

It's not surprising that companies leading the way in technological innovation and revenue generation also achieve higher rankings in terms of CSR initiatives. Beyond being a gauge of responsible and ethical corporate conduct, CSR activities contribute significantly to shaping the identity of various enterprises (McWilliams and Siegel, 2001). Presently, the sentiments of customers wield substantial influence on market valuation. This sentiment's significance has been acknowledged by numerous executives who affirm the pivotal role of CSR activities for companies, as a brand's reputation can be either constructed or dismantled by societal perceptions. This trend is exemplified by the escalating number of companies adopting CSR initiatives (rising from 46% in 2010 to 65% in 2014). Contributing positively to the community not only garners public favor but also enhances the perceived value of a brand, ultimately yielding returns that surpass the investment made.

Nowadays, companies spanning various industries are under significant pressure to not only function as successful enterprises but also to actively contribute to positive societal progress. These entities are now anticipated to collaborate closely with customers in the pursuit of creating a better world. Facilitating this transformation is social media, a pivotal tool in the realm of corporate social responsibility for multiple reasons. Among these, it serves as a platform for stakeholder dialogue, enabling the communication of CSR activities; it wields the power to influence consumers' informed decisions, and it plays a role in empowering employees to act as agents of change. Moreover, the impact of CSR initiatives presented online is noteworthy in terms of shaping consumers' purchasing behaviors in a favorable manner. Furthermore, employees are more inclined to align themselves with socially responsible organizations that effectively showcase their CSR efforts through social media channels (Ali *et al.*, 2015). The subsequent sections of the literature review delve into the existing body of knowledge regarding the Factors Influencing the Adoption of Social Media for Promoting Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).

CSR Communication: The presence of brands and companies in the new digital environments and social platforms has become an undeniable reality due to the advantages they offer for business and promotional communication. Social media is continually reshaping the tools employed for brand communication, playing a pivotal role in disseminating information about a company's brand. Additionally, organizations are harnessing social media networks to cultivate trust among customers (Khadim *et al.*, 2018). As a result, the cultivation of *brand loyalty* stands as a crucial factor in the promotion of CSR initiatives. In the current social networking platforms, customers increasingly seek a more intimate, transparent, and committed relationship with brand firms. This environment aims to be both consumer-friendly and beneficial for both parties involved (Ros-Diego and Castelló-Martínez, 2012). A company's capability to respond to stakeholder demands and engage in effective communication holds the potential to foster trust and legitimacy through ethical corporate conduct (Capriotti and Moreno, 2007). Through the utilization of social media communication, marketing professionals can comprehend consumers better by creating brand communities that enhance trust among customers (Khadim *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, effective communication of responsible behavior to stakeholders stands as a paramount concern and a pivotal element in the management of corporate responsibility. This is particularly crucial given that any misrepresentative corporate communication could not only be counterproductive but also severely jeopardize a *company's reputation*. Transparent communication regarding CSR practices serves as a means to cultivate corporate reputation (Chaudhri and Wang, 2007). Research conducted previously has revealed that social media serves as a platform where both companies and users contribute to shaping brand communication, leading to a favorable effect on brand awareness and the establishment of brand loyalty (Schivinski and Dabrowski, 2015). In light of this, businesses are recommended to adopt interactive CSR communication strategies. Consequently, it becomes imperative to modify the existing methods of CSR communication within firms, transitioning towards a *two-way communication* paradigm. This adjustment is essential to effectively promote CSR initiatives by actively engaging with their stakeholders (Cortado and Chalmeta, 2016).

Social Media types: The prevalent *social media platforms* utilized include Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, as well as user information services like Rich Site Summary (RSS) and blogs. This observation was made by Buigues-Garcia and Gimenez-Chornet (2012), as well as Xie and Stevenson (2014). The healthcare sector has yet to fully tap into the potential of social networks, despite the advantages and opportunities they hold. Properly harnessed, these platforms could lead to healthcare innovation and confer a competitive edge upon organizations (Sarringhaus, 2011). The adoption of social networks within any business realm is significantly

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influenced by factors such as technological maturity, laws pertaining to information and communication, and the level of public readiness. The primary drivers behind adopting social networks lie in environmental and organizational considerations. For healthcare organizations, the incorporation of social media is of paramount importance, serving as a means to connect with patient populations and establish a strategic advantage (Vinke and Lonergan, 2011). When harnessed effectively, social networks become invaluable tools through which healthcare organizations can engage users and offer consumers personalized experiences. This strategic shift represents an organizational change that aligns the modern workforce with the dynamics of the digital era (Sarringhaus, 2011). Studies indicate that web technology has evolved into a vital tool for facilitating the communication of corporate social responsibility matters. However, its application tends to be confined to specific content areas (Moreno and Capriotti, 2009). Consequently, the prominence of social networks plays a pivotal role in advancing CSR initiatives within the healthcare sector.

Blogs serve as a platform for individuals to express their perspectives and insights across a range of topics, often presented in a series of posts. Furthermore, they facilitate online dialogues and allow readers to provide comments on published content, contributing to interactive discussions (Buigues-Garcia and Gimenez-Chornet, 2012; Xie and Stevenson, 2014). In the contemporary digital landscape, blogs are aligned with a business-oriented approach, fostering increased customer engagement (Ros-Diego and Castello-Martinez, 2012). Utilizing social networks in a more advanced manner involves the incorporation of multimedia elements, particularly videos. This includes interactive CSR reports and *videos*, which can prove to be advantageous, given the widespread adoption of multimedia, such as streaming videos and advertisements, within the CSR domains of many companies (Chaudhri and Wang, 2007). In the modern digital landscape, the integration of videos into social networks aligns with a business-oriented strategy, contributing to the cultivation of social branding (Ros-Diego and Castello-Martinez, 2012).

A *web design platform* holds the potential to effectively propagate CSR information. A research undertaken by Chaudhri and Wang (2007) highlighted a concerning trend: a significant number of corporate websites lack comprehensive CSR information, and even prominent companies fail to capitalize on their websites as a means to effectively communicate CSR endeavors. Evidently, companies acknowledge the significance and necessity of showcasing their social commitments in a distinctive manner. Building upon this, Moreno and Capriotti (2009) proposed that the presence of a dedicated section devoted to CSR signifies a clear recognition of its importance. Such a designated space enables users to gain a comprehensive and expansive understanding of a company's corporate responsibility initiatives. Ultimately, incorporating website localisation becomes an imperative for any company aspiring to extend its products and services to a global audience. Employing social media for external interactions contributes to both localization efforts and the assimilation of external knowledge, thereby facilitating the extraction of pertinent insights from customers (Schlagwein and Hu, 2017). Consequently, *website localisation* brings about distinct advantages, particularly in terms of enhancing appeal and promoting CSR initiatives.

Social media benefits: Online social networks have become integral components of business strategies, with a noticeable surge in the utilization of social media as a marketing channel in recent times (Ros-Diego and Castelló-Martínez, 2012). Despite this trend, there is a lack of information pertaining to the factors that drive the adoption of social media within the UAE healthcare industry for the promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). Historically, social media has proven to be a potent tool for marketing endeavors and the endorsement of consumer products (Gazal *et al.*, 2016). Notably, Dlamini and Johnston (2018) identified organizations' utilization of social media as a dynamic force for advertising, marketing, and nurturing customer relationships across diverse platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and others. This multifaceted approach has been linked to bolstering organizational prominence, fostering relationships, enhancing brand identity, and attracting a wider customer base.

The study conducted by Tourani (2022) highlighted the crucial role of social media in business development strategies, which are essential components for enhancing business performance. This research also underscored the impact of social media on an organization's operations, revealing a significant link to the overall performance of the firm. Interestingly, the potency of different social media types displayed substantial variability. Hence, it becomes paramount for firms to comprehend, differentiate between, and harness the distinctive impacts of various media sources when formulating their social media marketing strategies. The significance of social network popularity cannot be overstated when it comes to promoting engagement and interaction within the community. Despite any negative perceptions that might circulate in the media about specific social media platforms, their popularity continues to make them a pivotal means of connecting and communicating with audiences (Chaffey, 2018). Consequently, the prominence of *social network popularity* stands as a pivotal factor in advancing Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives within the healthcare sector. social media platforms are acknowledged as community-centered avenues for organizations to engage, collect insights, and offer feedback to customers and members of society, all while maintaining a cost-efficient and highly effective approach. One of the notable attributes of social media tools for organizations is their accessibility and cost-effectiveness (Kargaran *et al.*, 2017).

Social media offers organizations a means to efficiently and economically connect with their customer base, streamlining outreach efforts in terms of both cost and time. Consequently, forward-thinking enterprises are presently channeling investments toward optimizing their social media presence as a platform to disseminate and convey their company's products and services (Kargaran *et*

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al., 2017). Consequently, the *costs associated* with maintaining a social network presence play a pivotal role in the integration of social media channels for the advancement of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) within the healthcare sector. Given the imperative nature of patient rights procedures, the *timely response* to issues and inquiries holds considerable importance for patients (Tutuncu *et al.*, 2014). The advent of digitalization within the realm of social media has notably impacted real-time communication (Ros-Diego and Castelló-Martínez, 2012). Consequently, it is foreseeable that social media platforms offering *real-time communication* capabilities will play a significant role in the promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) within the healthcare sector. It's well acknowledged that enterprises demonstrating social responsibility contribute to the enhancement of their brand, value, and overall reputation, ultimately leading to improved profitability (Ros-Diego and Castelló-Martínez, 2012).

Leveraging social media platforms to communicate corporate social responsibility initiatives to stakeholders and the broader society can lead to heightened engagement among stakeholders and society members (Zizka, 2017). Consequently, the strategic utilization of social media holds the potential to bolster *profitability* within the healthcare sector. Employing social media for the promotion of CSR entails a fundamental requirement: the company must effectively convey a sustained commitment to environmental and social undertakings in which it collaborates. This *commitment*, coupled with the active *promotion* of CSR, is fostering a paradigm shift in modern businesses, wherein they are increasingly deriving enhanced value from adhering to CSR standard practices. In essence, social media networks have emerged as pivotal platforms for communication and advocacy of CSR endeavors, as they act as intermediaries for transmitting a company's core values (including collaboration, commitment, and transparency) to society members and, reciprocally, reflecting societal values back to the company (Ros-Diego and Castelló-Martínez, 2012). Enterprises are confronted with well-defined anticipations from consumers concerning their involvement in Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). This dynamic necessitates that they adopt a proactive and transparent stance when engaging with their target audiences. The significance of this approach lies in the fact that any instance of misleading corporate communication could have detrimental consequences, potentially undermining a company's *social capital*. The assertion made by Chaudhri and Wang (2007) highlights the criticality of forthright and authentic communication in upholding an organization's standing.

Stakeholders Expectations and Interests: Stakeholder expectations significantly shape the decision to use social media as a platform for promoting Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) within the healthcare sector. Various stakeholders, such as patients, employees, investors, communities, and regulatory entities, possess distinct anticipations regarding how healthcare institutions participate in CSR initiatives and convey these efforts using social media channels (Menon and George, 2018). A fundamental approach employed in CSR should demonstrate robust and efficient communication with diverse stakeholders and members of society to effectively convey a company's CSR endeavors via web applications. The incorporation of social media into Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is markedly influenced by stakeholders' expectations and concerns. Their role drives the promotion of transparency, interaction, and promptness, compelling businesses to leverage social media platforms to effectively convey their CSR initiatives. Stakeholder feedback becomes the compass for shaping CSR strategies, exerting influence over a company's standing and its adeptness in managing crises. Essentially, the presence of stakeholders on social media channels significantly sculpts a company's approach to integrating CSR within its operational framework (Luo *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, companies are required to amplify their CSR communication efforts, not solely for profit generation, but also to showcase their commitment towards promoting CSR. This approach holds significance, as it empowers both society members and stakeholders to exert greater influence in encouraging businesses to adopt more *responsible practices* (Cortado and Chalmeta, 2016).

The Stakeholder Satisfaction Index stands as a pivotal determinant in ensuring the effective integration and adoption of social media platforms. One illustrative facet of this is reflected in the measurement of customer satisfaction derived from their engagement with a company's social media presence (Culnan *et al.*, 2010). This strategic approach highlights the significance of evaluating stakeholders' contentment levels as they interact with a firm's various social media channels. Such interactions can encompass a range of activities, including but not limited to customer inquiries, feedback, and participation in discussions. Analyzing social media interaction metrics informs improved engagement strategies and content. Proactive efforts foster positive stakeholder experiences on these platforms.

Online CSR *communication's interactivity* remains limited, primarily due to a prevailing reactive interaction approach and a dearth of specialized focus within firms (Etter, 2013; Cuervo-Carabel *et al.*, 2023). However, an escalation in interactivity within CSR communication yields augmented emotional resonance and heightened message credibility, as demonstrated by Cortado and Chalmeta's study (2016), fostering a stronger sense of company identification. Moreover, a *lack of enthusiasm for interactivity* and subpar engagement on online social networks can detrimentally impact the company's image and reputation. The pivotal elements of engagement and interaction through social media serve as instrumental drivers for establishing robust connections with stakeholders and enhancing the uptake of social media platforms. Understanding stakeholders' expectations and interests is imperative for effectively harnessing the potential of online social networks (Cortado and Chalmeta, 2016). To this end, it's crucial to involve stakeholders like government bodies, trade associations, communities, and affiliated businesses in decision-making processes, as highlighted by Cuervo-Carabel *et al.*, 2023), who emphasized the potential for mutual value creation through an alignment of individual and organizational interactions.

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CSR Implementation strategy: Formulating a robust CSR communication strategy should inherently stimulate societal and stakeholder engagement by fostering a dynamic exchange of ideas on the CSR subject (Cortado and Chalmeta, 2016). Consequently, companies are advised to revise their approach towards online social media, capitalizing on its complete business potential through three pivotal components suggested by Cortado and Chalmeta (2016) and Culnan *et al.* (2010): (1) Mindful Adoption, (2) Absorptive Capacity, and (3) Community Building.

According to Cortado and Chalmeta (2016), practicing mindful adoption entails making informed choices about the selection and utilization of specific social media platforms while taking into account governance and risk management. The company should meticulously assess the adoption process, prioritizing business value. In this approach, careful consideration is given to the timing and manner of adopting the appropriate platform(s) (Culnan *et al.*, 2010). Social media's comparative advantage and the conscientious approach to its adoption, considering its visibility, significantly influence the organizational acceptance of social media (Araújo and Zilber, 2016). Employing a deliberate adoption strategy is perceived as a means to reduce ambiguity and facilitate sense-making strategies and processes. This approach compels individuals to articulate the rationale behind their choices. Therefore, an awareness of the enduring advantages of social media is crucial to enhance elements like brand recognition and customer engagement (Broekemier *et al.*, 2015).

Absorptive capacity is the second factor, it stands as the subsequent crucial element within the implementation strategy, encompassing the aptitude to identify and assimilate novel knowledge and subsequently capitalize on insights furnished by stakeholders (Cortado and Chalmeta, 2016; Hovorka and Larsen, 2006; Nguyen, 2009). This capacity gauges an organization's competence in effectively undergoing a learning process (Francalanci and Morabito, 2008). The concept of Absorptive Capacity, initially introduced by Wisdom *et al.* (2014), revolves around an organization's adeptness in effectively utilizing both new and established knowledge, impacting the adoption of technology in various stages. This proficiency is particularly significant as organizations rich in knowledge and competencies can seamlessly integrate innovation. Consequently, the extent of technology adoption is notably influenced by this capacity. Achieving higher levels of technology adoption hinges on the amalgamation of internal absorptive capabilities and top management reinforcement. Individual absorptive capacities, as highlighted by Gopalakrishna-Remani *et al.* (2018), Lowik *et al.* (2017), and Schlagwein and Hu (2017), play a pivotal role within knowledge management, fostering an organization's open innovation practices. Noteworthy is the augmentation of absorptive capacity and overall performance through social media, as emphasized by Choi *et al.* (2014). Acknowledging that external knowledge fuels novel ideas, the concept of an organization's proficiency in recognizing and disseminating knowledge underpins absorptive capacity.

The third element warranting attention within the implementation strategy pertains to *community building*, encompassing the cultivation of an environment that facilitates engagement and active involvement of society members (Cortado and Chalmeta, 2016). To gauge the effectiveness of community building efforts, companies should assess various factors, including (1) the community's size and its growth trajectory, (2) the extent of time spent by community members on the company's social media platforms, (3) the proportion of active participants from the society, (4) the nature of their engagement with shared social media content, (5) the quality and quantity of discussions about the company and its offerings, (6) the redistribution of firm content and its dissemination across different platforms, and (7) indicators such as the extent of retweets for the company's tweets (Culnan *et al.*, 2010).

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section discusses the research methods employed in this study, including approaches to gathering data and conducting analysis. The primary information was obtained via a questionnaire survey, which was administered to 12 professionals who lead communication and social media divisions within the healthcare sector. All respondents, with over a decade of experience in their domains, have been utilizing social media for over four years, positioning them as seasoned experts. As suggested by Danner *et al.* (2011), here, AHP is used to solve complex multi-criteria decision problems in the healthcare field; this is a powerful and flexible tool for both qualitative and quantitative multi-criterion problems. This study demonstrates the application of the AHP framework through an examination of the strategies employed by communication and social media teams within the healthcare sector. The selection of the AHP methodology is substantiated by the intent to delve into tangible real-world scenarios. The subsequent sections outline the research process and outcomes.

Overview of AHP – AHP is a methodology designed to assess both rational and irrational values based on their significance in decision-making, as described by Hussain *et al.* (2016), offers a structured approach for simulating human decision processes. It enables the examination of business criteria and strategic concepts within the context of intricate scenarios for a specific organization. Decision-makers have embraced AHP to untangle complex issues and establish priorities through the deconstruction of multi-level hierarchies. The utility of AHP's objective and criteria hierarchy, as highlighted by Ishizaka *et al.* (2012), has been demonstrated, introducing options for enhancing and comparatively evaluating firms' relative performance.

Research process – This exploratory case study aims to practically apply the provided framework, illustrating anticipated outcomes of specific strategies. All interviews were conducted with experts from the healthcare industry. The research process is depicted in

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Figure 1. This study presents a unique application of the AHP framework, seeking insights into the significance of factors impacting social media adoption for CSR promotion. The AHP questionnaire underwent validation with two experienced communication and social media professionals within the healthcare sector in the UAE. Consequently, the final questionnaire encompassed 21 sustainability sub-factors.

The model – As shown in Figure 1, the initial step in the model involves problem identification. The research seeks to identify, prioritize, and select factors influencing the adoption of social media for CSR promotion, utilizing management evaluations from the healthcare industry in the UAE. This particular sector has encountered challenges in adopting social media for CSR promotion due to limited acceptance from stakeholders and society members. This study's objective is to recognize the multi-criteria attributes tied to factors influencing social media adoption in CSR promotion. Figure 2 presents the hierarchy crafted through the AHP model. The second level enlists the five primary factors of the multi-criterion set. On the third level, there are 21 sub-factors that elucidate and gauge these main factors, categorized under the respective five level-2 factors.

Figure 1: Outline of applied AHP method (source: Hussain et al., 2016)

The questionnaire was structured using a nine-point scale, following the recommendation by Goyal *et al.* (2015) for pair-wise comparisons (refer to Table 2). The participants represented healthcare organizations that commenced their social media usage in 2016. Ten experts were identified through interactions with relevant departments, fulfilling specific criteria: a minimum of 5 years' experience in communication and social media, over 10 years in their respective fields, and a decade of involvement in the healthcare industry. These professionals held positions as section heads, department managers, and division directors in both the communications and social media divisions of their organizations. They possessed extensive knowledge of the business landscape, including intricacies related to social media and communication, and played integral roles in the decision-making process for social media implementation.

For the AHP model, gathering respondents' perspectives entails conducting face-to-face meetings. Cheng *et al.* (2001) and Drake *et al.* (2013) highlight that AHP can deliver dependable outcomes with a modest sample size. To mitigate the limitations arising from a small survey sample, AHP methodically evaluates the importance of each item through pairwise comparisons (Table 2), capturing respondents' judgments. The assessments for paired comparisons predominantly hinge on expertise in the domain and rational reasoning (Drake *et al.*, 2013). The geometric mean was used instead of the arithmetic mean to combine the individual pair-wise judgments and formulate pair-wise matrices, in accordance with the suggestion by Scala *et al.* (2016). For instance, if an assessor identifies that social media types carry a moderate significance compared to the implementation strategy, a rating of '3' is assigned to the former while the latter receives a rating of '1/3'. Upon completion of the evaluation, calculations are performed to determine the eigenvectors (indicating relative importance), global weights, and maximum eigenvalue (λ_{max}) for each matrix. To ensure the

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consistent evaluation of the pairwise comparison matrix, the consistency ratio (CR) of the estimated vector is computed using the maximum value as a reference index.

According to Drake *et al.* (2013), coherence is quantified as $CI = [(\lambda_{max} - n)/(n-1)]$. Furthermore, the CR is employed to gauge the adequacy of matrix consistency. The CR is derived from the ratio of CI to the random index (RI), represented as $CR = CI/RI$. To establish the RI, random pair-wise comparisons are simulated to calculate average random indices for matrices of varying sizes. The specific values for RI can be found in Table 3 of Drake *et al.* (2013).

Figure 2 - AHP model for measuring Factors Influencing Social Media Adoption in Promoting CSR

Table 2. The 1–9 scale for AHP pairwise comparison.

Intensity of importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two criteria contribute equally to the objective of waste reduction
3	Moderate importance	Judgment slightly favour one over another
5	Strong importance	Judgment strongly favour one over another
7	Very strong importance	A criterion is strongly favoured and its dominance is demonstrated in practice
9	Absolute importance	Importance of one over another affirmed on the highest possible order
2,4,6,8	Intermediate values	Used to represent a compromise between the priorities listed above

Table 3. Random index.

N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
RI	0.00	0.00	0.58	0.90	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45	1.48

According to Drake *et al.* (2013), the inconsistency of a matrix is acceptable if its CR is less than or equal to 0.10. Table 4 reports the pair-wise comparison of the five main criteria, using average analysis in addition to the priority vectors for each factor.

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IV. ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

In Table 4, it's evident that respondents accorded the highest significance to the implementation strategy attribute, assigning it a priority weight of 34%. Following closely was Stakeholders' Expectations & Interests, with a competitive priority of 21%. Social media types and the advantages of social media ranked third and fourth, respectively, while CSR communication was deemed the least critical attribute by the assessors. For a deeper comprehension of the priorities outlined in Table 5, a pair-wise comparison of sub-criteria within each factor was conducted. This process, based on a consensus among evaluators, aimed to verify whether the CR adhered to acceptable standards. As indicated in Table 5, each criterion has been subdivided into respective sub-criteria.

Table 5 shows the pairwise evaluation of the three sub-criteria within CSR Communication (Brand loyalty, Two-way communication, and Corporate Reputation) is illustrated. The respondents attributed the highest overall significance to Two-way communication, assigning it a priority weight of 58%. Following this, Brand loyalty and Corporate Reputation held priorities of 26% and 17%, respectively. Examining the sub-criteria for Social Media Types (Table 5), the breakdown consists of Online Social Networks, Blogs, Localization Services, Video Sharing Sites, and CSR Web Design and Content. Video Sharing Sites emerged as the most pivotal, carrying a weight of 26%, closely trailed by Online Social Networks at 23%. Blogs and Localization Services followed suit, with weights of 22% and 16% respectively, while CSR Web Design and Content bore the lightest weight at 13%. Notably, within the realm of social media types, the evaluators acknowledged Video Sharing Sites as the most crucial sub-criterion, a sentiment echoed in previous research by Shihab (2015).

The benefits of social media were assessed through six sub-criteria: Worldwide Popularity, Low Implementation Cost, Ease of Real-time Measurements, Profit Generation, Commitment to & Promotion of CSR, and Building Social Capital. The prioritization of these sub-criteria is displayed in Table 5, where the rankings from pair-wise comparisons are presented. Among these, Low Implementation Cost emerged with the greatest weight of 27%, while Worldwide Popularity attained the lowest weight at 6%. The remaining four sub-criteria (Ease of Real-time Measurements, Profit Generation, Commitment to & Promotion of CSR, and Building Social Capital) occupied intermediate positions. As portrayed in Table 5, a comparative evaluation of Stakeholder's Expectations & Interests criteria is presented. Among these, Stakeholders' Disinterest emerged as the top priority, carrying a priority weight of 39%, followed by Public Satisfaction with a priority weight of 34%. Both Pressures for Responsible Action and Companies' Lack of Interest in Interactivity held equivalent priority weights of 14% within the Implementation Strategy sub-criteria. Respondents accorded the highest priority to Mindful Adoption, assigning it a weightage of 41%, followed by Absorptive Capacity with a competitive priority of 35%. Lastly, Community Building was rated least important, bearing a weight of 24%.

The concluding phase of the AHP involves determining the collective priority of the 21 indicators by multiplying the sub-criteria rankings with the criteria priority matrix (Figure 3). Leading the list, Mindful Adoption secured the highest position with a value of 13.85%. Notably, Mindful Adoption was a component of the implementation strategy, identified as the foremost criterion. Following closely, Absorptive Capacity obtained the second spot with an overall priority of 11.78%, also being a part of the implementation strategy. The Stakeholders' Disinterest sub-criterion claimed an 8.19% ranking. Community Building garnered an overall priority of 8.09%, while Public Satisfaction held a position of 7.11%. Two-way Communication scored at 6.43%, with Worldwide Popularity attaining the lowest rank at 0.91%.

Table 4. Geometric means of pair-wise comparison of main criteria.

Criteria	A	B	C	D	E	Priority vector
A. CSR Communication	0.10	0.08	0.21	0.09	0.08	0.11
B. Social Media Types	0.21	0.18	0.27	0.09	0.24	0.20
C. The advantages of social media	0.06	0.09	0.14	0.22	0.19	0.14
D. Stakeholders Expectations & Interests	0.20	0.38	0.12	0.19	0.16	0.21
E. Implementation Strategy	0.43	0.26	0.25	0.40	0.34	0.34
CR value=0.08<0.1 (Consistent)						

Table 5 -Geometric means for pair-wise comparison of sub-criteria.

(1) CSR Communication						
Criteria	A	B	C			Priority vector
A. Brand loyalty	0.44	0.17	0.16			0.26
B. Two-way communication	0.46	0.70	0.57			0.58
C. Corporate Reputation	0.10	0.14	0.26			0.17
CR Value: 0.01<0.1 (Consistent)						
(2) Social Media Types						
Criteria	A	B	C	D	E	Priority vector

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A. Online social networks	0.18	0.10	0.24	0.50	0.12		0.23
B. Blogs	0.43	0.24	0.26	0.16	0.03		0.22
C. Localisation Services	0.15	0.19	0.20	0.10	0.14		0.16
D. Video Sharing Sites	0.07	0.19	0.25	0.20	0.59		0.26
E. respo CSR Web design and Content	0.17	0.28	0.05	0.04	0.12		0.13
CR Value: 0.08<0.1 (Consistent)							

(3) The advantages of social media							
Criteria	A	B	C	D	E	F	Priority vector
A. Worldwide Popularity	0.06	0.07	0.04	0.04	0.09	0.08	0.06
B. Low implementation cost	0.06	0.23	0.20	0.46	0.47	0.22	0.27
C. Ease of Real-time measurements	0.31	0.23	0.20	0.17	0.04	0.17	0.19
D. Profit generation	0.28	0.09	0.22	0.18	0.21	0.11	0.18
E. Commitment to & promotion of CSR	0.13	0.05	0.18	0.05	0.10	0.22	0.12
F. Building Social Capital	0.16	0.13	0.15	0.09	0.09	0.21	0.14
CR Values: 0.08<0.1 (Consistent)							

(4) Stakeholder's Expectation & Interests					
Criteria	A	B	C	D	Priority vector
A. Pressure for Responsible Action	0.28	0.11	0.08	0.08	0.14
B. Public Satisfaction	0.33	0.34	0.37	0.31	0.34
C. Stakeholders disinterest	0.25	0.40	0.43	0.48	0.39
D. Companies lack of interest in interactivity	0.15	0.15	0.12	0.13	0.14
CR Value: 0.09<0.1 (Consistent)					

(5) Implementation Strategy				
Criteria	A	B	C	Priority vector
A. Mindful Adoption	0.44	0.21	0.61	0.42
B. Community Building	0.38	0.29	0.12	0.24
C. Absorptive Capacity	0.18	0.49	0.27	0.32
CR Value: 0.09<0.1 (Consistent)				

Figure 3. The overall priority of the 21 sub-criteria

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V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The user-centric framework, "Factors Influencing Social Media Adoption in Promoting," aims to aid healthcare decision-makers in assessing social media adoption factors. It enables the selection of options that impact social media adoption for CSR promotion in healthcare. This study demonstrates the framework's use by analyzing strategies of healthcare communication and social media teams. The study addresses a literature gap by identifying and ranking factors influencing social media adoption for CSR promotion in healthcare using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) (Drake et al., 2013). Determinants were derived from responses to a questionnaire targeting senior communication and social media personnel in an Abu Dhabi healthcare organization. Among the five criteria, Implementation Strategy held the highest weight at 34%, followed by Stakeholders' Expectations & Interests at 21%, and Social Media Types at 20%. The study aligns with prior research highlighting the importance of strategic social media integration (Matikiti *et al.*, 2018). This underscores the need for healthcare decision-makers to prioritize effective social media marketing strategies, embracing mindful adoption, absorptive capacity, and community building. This resonates with studies emphasizing the pivotal role of implementation strategy in maximizing social media's business value (Cortado and Chalmers, 2016; Sarringhaus, 2011).

Previous studies have explored Stakeholders' Expectations & Interests in CSR communication, amplifying stakeholder engagement (Zizka, 2017). With growing demands for transparency and dialogue, engaging with stakeholders is crucial (Luo et al., 2023). This study highlights two-way communication's importance for CSR recognition and social media adoption (Zizka, 2017). This aligns with research emphasizing two-way communication's role in maximizing social media's value. Rapid technological changes make social media adoption vital for shaping stakeholder perspectives. The study emphasizes the link between implementation strategy, healthcare communication, and CSR promotion among UAE consumers. The impact of strategies like Mindful Adoption, Community Building, and Absorptive Capacity is significant. As multinational organizations enter the UAE market, healthcare sectors must recognize implementation strategy's role in social media adoption. This study provides healthcare organizations and researchers with a comprehensive framework detailing the factors influencing social media adoption for CSR promotion, especially within the context of a developing economy. The primary findings emphasize that Implementation Strategy, Stakeholders' Expectations & Interests, and Social Media Types hold significant influence.

VI. IMPLICATIONS AND LIMITATION

This study investigates how social media can enhance Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in the UAE healthcare sector. It identifies key success factors based on impact, urgency, and priority, including CSR communication, types of social media, their benefits, stakeholder expectations, and an implementation strategy. The findings guide the UAE healthcare industry in prioritizing these factors to bolster their CSR image. These insights are relevant for other sectors pursuing CSR promotion through social media. Future research could refine measurement techniques and learn from companies across industries that have effectively adopted social media for CSR. Additionally, Future research could explore novel approaches to adopting social media, including gauging stakeholder and societal engagement levels. The current literature lacks a comprehensive understanding of factors driving social media's CSR promotion in healthcare. However, this study bridges this gap by introducing an innovative Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) framework. Results highlight the critical roles of Implementation Strategy, Stakeholders' Expectations & Interests, and Social Media Types in influencing CSR promotion through social media in healthcare. This underscores the need for healthcare decision-makers to align policies and strategies with intrinsic and extrinsic aspects of CSR via social media adoption. The study is limited to Abu Dhabi and suggests further research for wider coverage. Validation of the proposed AHP framework using methods like structural equation modeling is recommended. This work benefits researchers exploring implementation strategies and stakeholder expectations, while practitioners gain a practical tool to prioritize social media choices for CSR promotion. The framework aids communication and social media teams by categorizing options into five preference levels. Furthermore, Exploring the framework's effectiveness across industries could identify adaptations for specific contexts. It's crucial to recognize that the assumption of healthcare decision-makers thoroughly considering preferences might not universally hold due to constraints. While providing valuable insights, further research is needed to enhance and apply these findings across different sectors and situations.

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